

IMPROVING MARKETING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes ways to improve marketing in the development of export of agricultural products of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Measures for the development of the field are indicated.

Key words: agriculture, export, marketing, development, products.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МАРКЕТИНГА В РАЗВИТИИ ЭКСПОРТА СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются пути совершенствования маркетинга при развитии экспорта сельскохозяйственной продукции Республики Узбекистан. Указаны меры по развитию месторождения.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, экспорт, маркетинг, развитие, продукция.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the country is implementing comprehensive measures aimed at expanding the production, storage, processing and export of fruits and vegetables. In order to implement projects for the intensive development of fruit and vegetable growing, acreage has been significantly expanded, additional capacities for storage and processing of fruits and vegetables have been launched, financial resources are attracted, including funds from international financial institutions. actively involved. For example, in January-December 2019, 8% of investments in the amount of 189924.3 billion soums were directed to the agricultural sector. As a result, the volume of agricultural production in the current year amounted to 215.7 trillion soums or 102.7% compared to 2018, including agricultural products - 108.3 trillion soums (103.7%), livestock products - 107, 4 trillion soums (101.7%). It should be borne in mind

With the abolition of the cotton monopoly, the main areas are divided into horticulture, viticulture, horticulture and viticulture. At the same time, new agricultural products are being imported into our country, which are highly valued on the world market. The following table presents the dynamics of agricultural production in the Republic of Uzbekistan. (Table 1)

Table 1

Information on the cultivation of agricultural products in Uzbekistan in 2018-2020

t/r	Name of agricultural product	Production capacity, thousand tons			
		2018	2019	Growth,%	January-September 2020
one	Flakes	6375.4	7187.4	112.7	6667.1
2	Potato	2750.1	2950.9	107.3	2432.1
3	Vegetables	9635.1	9945.4	103.2	7630.4
4	melons	1904.9	1922.2	100.9	1399.1
5	Fruits and berries	2589.7	2739.6	105.8	2067.7
6	Grape	1564.5	1595.2	101.9	1275.3
	TOTAL	24820	26341	106.1	21472

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

From the data in the table, we can conclude that the volume of agricultural production in the country is growing. We are seeing an increase in the physical size of almost all types of crops. According to the results of the first nine months of 2020, despite the difficult year, the volume of production is growing.

The issue of strengthening reforms in the agro-industrial complex remains relevant for our country. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan March 14, 2019 "On measures to develop agricultural cooperation in the field of fruits and vegetables Concentration No. PQ-4239PQ-4549 dated 12/11/2019 "On additional measures for the further development of the fruit and vegetable and viticulture industry, the creation of value chains in the industry"-numbered In their decisions The goal is to stimulate the creation of value chains in the fruit and vegetable sector, ensure the sustainability of the production and export of quality fruits and vegetables, expand the financial capabilities of producers, and increase the competitiveness of products..

At the same time, the high level of competition in foreign fruit and vegetable markets requires the prompt introduction of modern methods of agricultural technology and management of production and supply processes.

The use of advanced crop production technologies, the introduction of modern methods of processing and storage of products in the sustainable development of the fruit and vegetable sector will make it possible to prevent food shortages today. It is known that grown fruits and vegetables go through a number of technological processes until they reach the consumer in the form of finished products. Not only to prevent the death of fruits and vegetables, but also to expand the sown area and increase the gross harvest, which places great challenges on specialists in this field. To do this, first of all, great attention should be paid to the selection of varieties and agrotechnical processing processes. As fruits and vegetables ripen, it is better to pick them in a timely manner and deliver them to the next stages as needed. A promising direction is also to increase the range of exports of agricultural products.

World experience shows that competitiveness and access to world markets, first of all, due to the gradual reform of the economy, deepening structural reforms and diversification, ensuring the rapid development of new high-tech enterprises and industries, modernizing existing industries and effective use of marketing technologies. feasible.

The results of studies conducted in developed countries show that taking into account internal factors that can be controlled, including brand, price, location and market access, determines the effectiveness of marketing. However, many horticultural producers do not control these factors when organizing marketing management. Entering foreign markets with agricultural products requires a lot of preparation, full implementation of marketing activities, and extensive use of export infrastructure. It is especially important to create a marketing strategy to capture foreign markets. Today we are seeing low attention to the marketing activities of exporting farms. For instance,

Having studied their concept and approaches, we can conclude that they do not have a well-defined strategy for interacting with manufacturers to bring their products to the end consumer.

If we consider the problems in the field of marketing, we can see the relevance of a deep study of the foreign market, bringing the product to the market, carefully considering the system

of its distribution. In many cases, the organization of marketing activities is limited to the purchase, storage, transportation, and the distribution of goods, i.e., its implementation, is not given much attention. It is known that the sale of produced vegetables and fruits and the purchase of raw materials are a key factor in the development of the industry, and these factors should underlie the marketing strategy of the company.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The above resolutions of the President of the country set the task "to approve the procedure for granting subsidies to exporters of fruits and vegetables to cover 50% of the costs associated with conducting marketing research on foreign markets for fruits and vegetables produced by members of agricultural associations."

We can see the role of marketing in agricultural exports from the characteristics of these products. First of all, the rapid wear of products determines the short period of its implementation. In addition, the appearance of the product requires great attention to packaging in order to meet the standard of this market. If we add to this the consideration of sanitary requirements, we can see how important marketing is in the export of vegetables and fruits. When organizing the marketing of fruit and vegetable products in countries with developed market economies, it is clear that producers quickly and accurately study changes in consumer demand and take appropriate measures. Therefore, in order for marketing in agricultural enterprises to be successful, business leaders need to clearly define the tasks, make a decision based on reliable information about its current financial and financial situation. In general, rather than relying on export infrastructure, farmers themselves need to plan and implement marketing activities.

In our opinion, the current state of fruit and vegetable marketing should force the heads of agricultural enterprises to find answers to the following questions in order to assess their position in the domestic and foreign markets and, ultimately, determine the marketing strategy. ;

what changes are taking place in foreign markets, how competitive forces affect;

how the enterprise works, i.e. whether it is necessary to analyze the current state of the enterprise;

why it occupies a low price segment of the market where it sells export agricultural products;

what needs to be done to improve product quality and export potential in order to increase profits;

whether a business plan is developed for each product released and whether this plan is analyzed in the chain of delivery of the product to the consumer.

At most enterprises in the network, marketing tasks are assigned to certain external structures, which is absolutely wrong. External infrastructure entities should not only engage in marketing work, but also help farmers increase their export potential. It is necessary to develop views on the concept of marketing in agriculture as a business philosophy that requires the support of all workers and employees in the industry.

In recent years, the agricultural sector has been actively reformed in the country. In order to improve the management system in this area, introduce effective mechanisms of state support, establish cooperation, introduce modern resource-saving technologies, and increase the volume of agricultural exports, a number of decrees and resolutions have been adopted. However, at a

time when sales of fruit and vegetable products on the world market amounted to 205 billion US dollars, the share of the republic in this market less than one percent. The share of these products in the country's exports is 7 percent.

DISCUSSION

Uzbekistan has a huge potential for the production (growing) of fruits and vegetables and the development of their export to foreign markets. But it is important to remember that potential and its realization are two different concepts. Much is currently being done in Uzbekistan to increase agricultural production, but an increase in production (cultivation) does not automatically lead to an increase in exports. The reason is that when exporting, first of all, it is necessary to understand what kind of product a potential consumer needs and what he needs. It must also answer questions such as who the real consumer is and what countries they live in. Also, when it comes to fruit exports,

For example, in the European Union there is almost no demand for vegetables and fruits that do not fall into the "premium" category. The situation is similar in the US and many other developed countries. In addition, each country has specific requirements and needs for different characteristics of fruits in terms of their color, taste, caliber and other characteristics.

In other words, every entrepreneur must start with strategic decisions, a correct understanding of the market when exporting. Otherwise, there may be no demand for its products at all. Such cases are not uncommon in Uzbekistan. But growing a crop is not even half the battle. When growing vegetables and fruits, it is very important to take into account factors such as their quality (without loss of properties or maximum safety), certain shelf life and packaging. In most cases, the costs and investments in the post-harvest process exceed the costs of growing the product, and often such costs are underestimated.

This issue should always be considered in the light of current climatic conditions. In Uzbekistan, you can grow products with unique properties. But there is no point in growing apples for export, with the exception of some early varieties of apples. Another important factor in this regard is the geographical remoteness of Uzbekistan from all external markets (for the export of fruits and vegetables). This means that the cost of delivering a product to consumers, i.e. logistics costs, is always high. Therefore, it makes no sense to export cheap products - margins for profitable exports may not be enough. It is also necessary to take advantage of the country's labor force - the more laborious and costly the harvesting process, the chances of Uzbekistan to export this product will be so high. Of course the quality

For the first 8 months of this year, Uzbekistan exported 12.9 thousand tons of greens to the Russian market and for the first time became the largest importer of greens in the Russian market. The share is 40 percent. **Temporarily due to current green export issues and other factors** we can talk about a stable trend. In addition, the cultivation of greenery and its export is exactly the segment that I spoke about above. Given the existing natural and climatic conditions, the fact that the cultivation of this crop requires a lot of labor and the cost of the product is quite high, you can not worry about high transportation costs. True, Uzbekistan can earn more on the export of greens to other countries. Because "dill" and "parsley" are the cheapest varieties of greens, and import prices are the lowest in Russia and Ukraine. This means that Uzbekistan sells cheap greens at the lowest prices. Accordingly, the

requirements for product quality are also much lower. But if we put a little more effort into growing greenery and exporting it,

As mentioned above, the cultivation of agricultural products today is not half the process that covers the “distance” from the field to the consumer. An important task is to deliver these products to supermarket shelves with the maximum preservation of their properties, especially if these supermarkets are located several thousand kilometers away (if we are talking about exports). The organization of storage and logistics of agricultural products today has become a whole infrastructure, and its marketing is one of the directions of the economy.

One of the most common mistakes that many make when planning business plans in agriculture is that they focus on the cost of production (growing) of the product. But the cost of the infrastructure to store the product and turn it into a finished product for consumption tends to be more expensive than building a garden, per hectare. Many do not understand this.

The second common mistake is that marketing costs are not included in any business plan. Many in Uzbekistan expect support or some kind of support from the state. Both approaches are wrong. Only effective marketing can help you make a profit, and everything else is a cost. It should be understood that there is no shortage of products today in any part of the world. But marketing isn't free—it comes at a cost. For example, participation in exhibitions, visits to business partners, negotiations, etc. All this is not cheap.

The third mistake is to "burden" the business intermediary with the cost of storing the product, turning it into a finished product for the consumer, marketing. First of all, the products to be stored should be stored in warehouses close to the field, because for such products every hour is a trophy. If these products are not placed in special conditioned warehouses shortly after harvest, their quality may deteriorate drastically. Therefore, the storage of products is not a separate business - all over the world, private warehouses are owned by agricultural producers or their cooperatives. In other words, this business is under the control of the manufacturers. With a sufficient number of special warehouses, the possibility of obtaining additional income through the storage of products is practically absent.

If the marketing costs are "assigned" to the business intermediary, almost all the profit will remain with him. As long as this approach is acceptable, you can continue to work in this style.

CONCLUSION

First of all, the mentality interferes, that is, “there is no shortage of products and there will not be, instead of trying to sell the grown product, customers and consumers are interested in what kind of product is needed, to ensure the appropriate and necessary quality, variety, taste, caliber, packaging, etc. .d." I think there is a misunderstanding here. When such a concept appears, then export growth and its diversification will begin. Only then will product manufacturers begin to understand why they need GlobalGAP and why it is important that there are no trifles in the production chain.

Currently, 99% of fruits and vegetables grown in Uzbekistan are of interest only in Russia and the CIS countries. Even in Russia, the market for these products is declining, as their main consumers are the elderly. The younger generation does not want to buy traditional Uzbek

grapes. They focus not on grapes in wooden boxes covered with gauze, but on seedless varieties that have become world famous, sold in convenient packaging.

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